

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component Evaluation of Literature Compounds as Lyn Chemical Probes

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Authors	Weerawarna, P. M.; Richardson, T. I.; Chu, S.; Mason, E. R.; ElJordi, O
Collaborating Authors	Jesudason, C. D.; Davis, C.; Angus, S.P.
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Affiliations	Indiana University School of Medicine and Purdue University

Introduction:

Lyn and Hck belong to the Src family tyrosine kinases (SFKs), where they share a similar structural architecture comprising multiple protein domains, including an N-terminal SH4 domain, a unique domain, SH3 and SH2 domains, and a catalytic SH1 domain (**Figure 1**).¹ Even though the primary function of both kinases is to phosphorylate the tyrosine residues of various cellular targets, Lyn in particular phosphorylates immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motifs (ITAMs) and immunoreceptor tyrosine-based inhibition motifs (ITIMs) of various activating and inhibitory cell surface receptors.² In fact, Lyn is one of the few SFKs known to phosphorylate ITAMs, along with Fyn and Lck. Interestingly, Lyn is the main SFK known to phosphorylate ITIMs associated with a wide range of inhibitory immune receptors, such as FcγRIIb, CD22, PIR-B, and SIRP1α.³ In addition to Lyn, c-Fgr, a lesser-known SFK, is reported to phosphorylate ITIMs of SIRP1α in macrophages.⁴ Hck, on the other hand, can also phosphorylate specific tyrosine residues of receptors, such as CD36, that are not part of ITAMs or ITIMs.⁵ However, it mostly phosphorylates protein targets that have enzymatic functions, such as Vav1, Cbl, and Stat5.⁵⁻⁸ Lyn expression is predominant in hematopoietic cells from both the myeloid and lymphoid lineages, excluding T cells.^{9, 10} Additionally, Lyn is expressed in the brain, especially in microglia, implying the existence of shared signaling mechanisms between the immune and central nervous systems.¹¹ Similarly, Hck is also reported to be expressed in hematopoietic cells and in the brain.^{10, 12} Due to the expression of both kinases in hematopoietic cells, they have been linked to various cancers and autoimmune diseases.^{13, 14}

Multiple genetic studies have connected AD risk and protective variants of genes such as TREM2, CD33, APOE, ABCA7, PLCG2, and INPP5D, which are key to microglial function, the resident phagocytes of the central nervous system.¹⁵ The SFKs became the subject of this study due to their differential expression and differential co-expression of clusters of genes (coexpression modules) that are dysregulated in AD compared to controls.¹⁶ The roles of Lyn and Hck in neurodegenerative diseases has recently been reported by others, with particular emphasis on Lyn as an emerging target for the treatment of such diseases.^{17, 18} Detailed RNA sequencing of AD and aging brains has identified a particular subset known as disease-associated microglia (DAMs), present in both humans and mice.¹⁹ According to the literature, microglial expression of Lyn increases in response to amyloid beta (Aβ), a primary pathological indicator of AD, in mouse models.²⁰ A higher Lyn expression has also been found in human and mouse microglia compared to other Src family kinases (SFKs).²¹ Furthermore, post-mortem AD patient brains have also shown elevated Lyn levels in microglia.²² Interestingly, the broad-spectrum Src kinase inhibitor

PPI, which mainly targets Lyn, was shown to inhibit A β -triggered neurotoxin production and improve neuronal survival.²² Additionally, independent studies have documented increased Lyn activation in mouse microglia exposed to A β oligomers, akin to the microglia from the post-mortem AD patient brains.^{23, 24}

Figure 1. Organization of human Lyn domains and the sequence comparison between the human (Uniport# P07948), mouse (Uniport# P25911), and rat (Uniport# Q07014) isoforms.

In a detailed study by Gwon et al., the role of Lyn in Alzheimer's disease (AD) was explored, revealing its significant involvement in amyloid beta (A β)-induced neurotoxicity and tau hyperphosphorylation via Fc γ RIIb2 phosphorylation.¹⁷ The study observed a rapid increase in Lyn activity upon exposure to oligomeric A β 1–42 in mouse neuronal cells. They also found that Lyn activation was inhibited in Fc γ RIIb2 knockout neurons, suggesting that Fc γ RIIb2-A β 1–42 interactions mediated the activation of Lyn. An analysis of AD patient brain tissue revealed a three-fold increase in Lyn's autophosphorylation in the hippocampus compared to non-AD controls. Further experimentations confirmed the direct phosphorylation of the Fc γ RIIb2 ITIM at Tyr273 by Lyn upon exposure to oligomeric A β 1–42. Interestingly, the knockdown of Lyn expression significantly suppressed A β 1–42-induced cell death in neuroblastoma and hippocampal cell lines, underscoring Lyn's role in countering A β 1–42-induced neurotoxicity. Additionally, phosphorylated Fc γ RIIb2 by Lyn was found to recruit SHIP2 to Fc γ RIIb2, leading to tau-hyperphosphorylation. Lastly, a novel Lyn inhibitor (KICG2576) was shown to lessen A β -Fc γ RIIb2-mediated neuronal cell death and rescue A β -induced memory impairment in mice. Overall, this study establishes the role of Lyn in Alzheimer's disease in the context of amyloid β (A β 1-42)-triggered neurotoxicity and tau hyperphosphorylation, which are the main pathological features of Alzheimer's disease.

TREM2 is a receptor expressed on the surface of microglia that binds A β and APOE and activates microglial cells for the clearance of extracellular debris.²⁵ The TREM2-mediated microglia activation is known

to be phagocytic and anti-inflammatory and one of the critical mechanisms for clearing A β plaques.^{26, 27} Hence, it has been considered an attractive therapeutic strategy in the treatment of AD in early stage. Lower TREM2 expression and hypomorphic variants increase the risk of AD, while the hypermorphic variant of PLCG2, PLCG2^{P522R}, downstream from TREM2, is protective.^{25, 28} TREM2 requires DAP12, an adapter protein on the intracellular side of the plasma membrane that associates with numerous signal transduction mediators and is phosphorylated by SFKs such as Fyn and Lyn.²⁹ The involvement of Lyn in TREM2-mediated microglia can be hypothesized because of the involvement of various activation and inhibitory immune receptors and adaptor proteins bearing ITAM and ITIMs such as DAP12, CD33, and Fc γ R11b.^{29, 30} However, the exact role of Lyn in TREM2-mediated microglia activation is unknown, and no studies have been reported to this date.

Figure 2. (A) Proposed role of Lyn in TREM2-mediated microglial activation and phagocytosis. **(B)** Role of Lyn in tau hyperphosphorylation (based on the findings from reference 15).

Based on the literature findings related to myeloid cells, several roles of Lyn in TREM2-mediated microglial activation and phagocytosis can be postulated, as depicted in **Figure 2**.³ The phosphorylation of inhibitory immune receptors such as CD33 and Fc γ R11b by Lyn might inhibit TREM2-mediated microglial activation through the activation of phosphatases such as SHIP1 and SHP1. In addition, Lyn can directly activate these phosphatases by phosphorylating them. Therefore, it could be hypothesized that inhibiting Lyn would enhance TREM2-mediated microglial activation and phagocytosis, which is known to be beneficial for treating early-stage Alzheimer's disease. On the other hand, inhibiting Hck, another Src kinase known to inhibit microglial activation and associated with the development of late-onset Alzheimer's disease in mice, might have different effects. Thus, when using Src kinase inhibitors to evaluate the role of Lyn kinase in TREM2-mediated microglial activation and phagocytosis, it's crucial to use inhibitors with significant selectivity for Lyn over Hck.

There are several reported Src kinase inhibitors with potent Lyn inhibitor activities. However, most are non-selective, or their selectivity is not reported. Furthermore, only a few efforts are reported in the literature that specifically focus on developing Lyn-specific inhibitors.^{31, 32} Therefore, as part of our ongoing drug discovery effort to develop Lyn-specific kinase inhibitors and determine the role of Lyn in TREM2-mediated microglia activation and phagocytosis, we profiled reported Lyn inhibitors and screened

for selective inhibitors in a series of assays to assess their potency, Lyn/Hck selectivity, and phagocytosis induction capability in HMC3 and BV2 cells. Here, we report these findings as well as the kinome profiles of selected inhibitors in HMC3 and BV2 cells.

Results:

Construction of the Literature Annotated Cassette and Evaluation of Lyn/Hck Inhibitor Activities.

As a starting point, we conducted an extensive literature survey and identified 14 potent Lyn kinase inhibitors, some of which also have reported Hck inhibitor activities.^{17,31-44} The chemical structures of these inhibitors are shown in **Figure 3**. The inhibitors mainly consist of type I and type II kinase inhibitors that target DFG-in active and DFG-out inactive kinase conformations, respectively. Compounds 13 and 14 are reported as potent type I_{1/2} Lyn inhibitors that target the alpha-C-out inactive kinase conformation, exhibiting over 200 and 30-fold selectivity for Lyn over Hck, respectively.³¹ However, upon close examination of the reported Lyn inhibitor activities of these selected compounds, we found that they had been evaluated using different assay protocols at various ATP concentrations.

To facilitate a direct comparison, we first evaluated the Lyn and Hck inhibitor activities of this annotated cassette using the Hotspot kinase assay according to a previously described protocol.⁴⁵ The corresponding substrate was first prepared in a freshly constituted base reaction buffer (20 mM Hepes (pH 7.5), 10 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM EGTA, 0.01% Brij35, 0.02 mg/ml BSA, 0.1 mM Na₃VO₄, 2 mM DTT, 1% DMSO) and necessary cofactors were introduced to the substrate solution. After that, the kinase was added, ensuring gentle mixing for a homogeneous solution. Using the Echo550 acoustic technology, inhibitors dissolved in 100% DMSO (10 mM) were introduced into the kinase-substrate-cofactor mixture in nanoliter volumes to create a 10-point, three-fold dilution series starting from 100, 10, or 1 μM inhibitor concentrations. This mixture was subsequently incubated at room temperature for 20 minutes to facilitate optimal interactions. The kinase reaction was initiated by adding 33P-ATP (10 μM) into the mixture. Following this, the reaction was allowed to proceed for 2 hours at room temperature to ensure completion. After the incubation, the kinase activity was detected using the P81 filter-binding method. The measured K_i values are shown in **Table 1** and **2**, along with the literature values.

As expected, all the inhibitors showed potent Lyn inhibitor activities confirming the literature reports. Type I inhibitors primarily demonstrated sub-nanomolar Lyn inhibitor activities, while type II inhibitors exhibited low nanomolar inhibitor activities. Several of these inhibitors also displayed significant selectivity for Lyn over Hck. Among the type I inhibitors, Bosutinib was the only inhibitor to demonstrate Lyn over Hck selectivity greater than 30-fold, followed by Saracatinib with a Lyn selectivity of 16-fold. Among the type II inhibitors, Imatinib, Masitinib, and AST-487 each displayed over 20-fold selectivity for Lyn (31.8, 23.8, and 23.1-fold, respectively).

Figure 3. Chemical structures of the literature compounds used in this study.

Interestingly, we did not observe the reported 200-fold Lyn over Hck selectivity for the two type I_{1/2} inhibitors, compounds 13 and 14, even though both exhibited low nanomolar Lyn inhibitor activities. After identifying a set of Lyn inhibitors from the literature with notable Lyn over Hck selectivities, we proceeded to test these compounds in a high-content imaging assay using the HMC3 (human) and BV2 (mouse) microglia-like cell lines with simultaneous measurement of phagocytosis, cell number, and nuclear area to elucidate their potential for activating microglia without cytotoxicity.

Table 1. Evaluation of the Lyn/Hck inhibitor activities of the literature compounds comparing measured K_i in hotspot assay to literature reported K_d or K_i

Comp:	Type	Hotspot K_i (nM)		Select:	Literature K_d (nM)		Literature Assay Note
		Lyn	Hck		Lyn	Hck	
2 ^(ref 41)	NA	0.12 ± 0.03	0.8 ± 0.2	6.2	2.2 (K_d)	3.2 (K_d)	Liganded beads-based qPCR assay
7 ^(ref 41)	II	2.1 ± 0.3	48 ± 23	23.1	14 (K_d)	880 (K_d)	Liganded beads-based qPCR assay
9 ^(ref 41)	II	32 ± 4	1020 ± 110	31.8	890 (K_d)	NF	Liganded beads-based qPCR assay
10 ^(ref 41)	II	47 ± 10	97 ± 21	2	100 (K_d)	390 (K_d)	Liganded beads-based qPCR assay
11 ^(ref 31)	II	4.1 ± 0.4	28 ± 1	6.9	19 (K_d)	NF	ELISA-based
13 ^(ref 30)	I _{1/2}	26 ± 5	38.5 ± 0.6	1.5	8.7 (K_i)	>2000 (K_i)	Fluorescent reporter assay
14 ^(ref 30)	I _{1/2}	4.3 ± 0.5	1.24 ± 0.05	0.3	61 (K_i)	>2000 (K_i)	Fluorescent reporter assay

^aThe IC₅₀ values were determined using the Hotspot kinase assay and converted to K_i values using the Cheng-Prusoff equation to facilitate direct comparison. The values are reported as average of two independent runs ± SD.

Table 2 Evaluation of the Lyn/Hck inhibitor activities of the literature compounds comparing measured K_i in hotspot assay to literature reported IC₅₀

Comp:	Type	Hotspot K_i (nM)		Select:	Literature IC ₅₀ (nM)		Literature Assay Note
		Lyn	Hck		Lyn	Hck	
1 ^(ref 33)	NA	0.06 ± 0.01	0.16 ± 0.00	3.2	<0.15	NF	10 uM ATP (Hotspot Kinase Assay)
3 ^(ref 42)	I	0.08 ± 0.01	3 ± 1	32.8	0.5	23	1 uM ATP
4 ^(ref 35, 37)	I	<0.03	0.28 ± 0.01	>9.3	0.85	NF	Radioactive kinase assay
5 ^(ref 38, 39)	I	0.27 ± 0.05	4.5 ± 0.6	16.7	5	NF	ELISA-based
6 ^(ref 15)	I	7.7 ± 0.9	59 ± 5	8	150	NF	1 mM ATP (Western Blot)
8 ^(ref 40)	II	11.1 ± 0.4	265 ± 24	23.8	500	2000	ELISA-based
12 ^(ref 32,43)	I _{1/2}	<0.03	0.21 ± 0.03	>7	29	0.43	1 mM ATP

^aThe IC₅₀ values were determined using the Hotspot kinase assay and converted to K_i values using the Cheng-Prusoff equation to facilitate direct comparison. The values are reported as average of two independent runs ± SD.

Evaluation of Phagocytosis Induction and SFK Selectivity

BV2 and HMC3 cells serve as *in vitro* models for studying microglial function, including phagocytosis, a critical process performed by microglia in the brain for innate immunity and tissue homeostasis. The BV2 cell line, an immortalized murine microglial cell line, often substitutes primary microglia in various studies due to its morphological and functional similarities, including the ability to perform phagocytosis.⁴⁶ The HMC3 cell line, a human microglial cell line, is used in research related to neurodegenerative diseases. Like BV2 cells, HMC3 cells also exhibit key microglial functions, such as

phagocytosis.⁴⁷ Therefore, as part of our preliminary study, we tested the aforementioned literature compounds in BV2 and HMC3 phagocytosis assays to evaluate the impact of Lyn inhibition on microglial activation and phagocytosis.

A phenotypic high-content imaging assay with simultaneous measures of phagocytosis, cell number, and nuclear intensity was used to assess both cellular pharmacology and cell health⁴⁸. Model cell lines BV2 (immortalized mouse microglia, a gift from Dr. Michelle Block's laboratory at IUSM) and HMC3 (immortalized human microglia, obtained from ATCC, CRL-3304) were used to provide adequate throughput. Cells were cultured in DMEM GlutaMax media (ThermoFisher) containing 10% FBS and Pen-Strep in a 37°C 5% CO₂ incubator, plated in Corning Falcon 384 well Optilux Black and clear bottom plates; 400 cells/45 µl/well (BV2 cells), 600 cells/45 µl/well (HMC3 cells) and 2000 cell/45 µl/well (primary cells), and treated with 10x serially diluted compounds (60 µM–3 nM) for 48 hrs at 37°C. The cells were then seeded with pHrodo-myelin (20 hrs total) 24 hrs after compound treatment initiation; 1 mg/ml (protein equivalent) pHrodo-myelin stocks were stored at -20°C or -80°C, thawed, diluted with culture media to produce a 10x seeding solution (50 µg/ml) and added to the 384-well plate (5 µl/well). Nuclear staining solution (1 µl of 10 mg/ml Hoechst-33342 per 1 ml culture media; 20 µl/well) was added to a final concentration of 2.5 µg/ml, and the plates were incubated for 30 min at 37°C and then scanned with an ArrayScan automatic high content imaging system (10x objective lens, 4 fields/well collected). Mean total phagocytosis spot intensity per cell, total cell counts per well, and mean average nuclear intensity per cell for cell health were measured. Cellular potencies for each endpoint (EC₅₀ for phagocytosis, IC₅₀ for cell count) were calculated using a four-parameter logistic curve regression model.

Among the 14 compounds tested, five demonstrated the ability to induce phagocytosis in at least one of the assays as indicated in **Table 3**. These compounds comprised two type I kinase inhibitors, Saracatinib and Bosutinib, and three type II kinase inhibitors, Nilotinib, Bafetinib, and Masitinib. Saracatinib exhibited excellent phagocytosis induction with an EC₅₀ value of 0.18 µM, and a maximum phagocytosis of 472%, followed by Bosutinib, which had an EC₅₀ value of 0.54 µM and a maximum phagocytosis of 304% (Figure 4 and 5). However, the phagocytic induction capability of these compounds was constrained to HMC3 cells and was absent in BV2 cells. In comparison to type I inhibitors, type II inhibitors demonstrated only moderate phagocytosis induction capabilities in one or both assays, predominantly at higher inhibitor concentrations. This observation might primarily be attributed to their low nanomolar Lyn inhibitor activities, as opposed to the sub-nanomolar Lyn inhibitor activities displayed by type I compounds. In some instances, the toxicity associated with higher inhibitor concentrations and higher nuclear intensity interfered with the accurate determination of the maximum phagocytosis percentage.

The five compounds that exhibited phagocytic activities were further evaluated for their selectivity among the Src-family kinases (SFKs) (**Table 3**). The two type I inhibitors, Saracatinib and Bosutinib, displayed sub-nanomolar inhibitory activities across all the SFKs, revealing their broad-spectrum SFK inhibitor characteristics. In contrast, type II inhibitors demonstrated some selectivity across the SFKs. Notably, Bafetinib appeared to selectively inhibit Lyn and Lck over other SFKs with inhibitor constants of 4.05 nM and 3.02 nM, respectively. Nilotinib and Masitinib also followed a similar trend and selectively inhibited Lyn and Lck over other SFKs. Interestingly, Nilotinib did not show significant inhibition of Src or Fyn at the highest inhibitor concentration of 10 µM, hindering the accurate determination of the inhibitor constants. This finding is in alignment with the reported literature values.

Figure 4. Representative phagocytosis assay curves for type I inhibitors (n=2 and curves are a representation of a single run)

Figure 5. Representative phagocytosis assay curves for type II inhibitors (n = 1)

Table 3. SFK selectivity and the phagocytosis induction assay results.

Inhibitor	K_i (nM) ^a					
	TAD-0000640	TAD-0410368	TAD-0410156	TAD-0410182	TAD-0410068	
Generic Name	Saracatinib	Bosutinib	Nilotinib	Bafetinib	Masitinib	
Inhibitor Type	I	I	II	II	II	
Lyn	0.27	<0.03	47.8	4.08	11.1	
Hck	4.52	0.28	96.6	28.4	265	
Blk	0.8	0.25	4181	126.45	156.9	
Src	0.4	0.1	ND ^b	290.75	541.92	
Fgr	4.91	0.23	236.07	23.31	126.33	
Fyn	5.97	0.4	ND ^b	117.9	58.67	
Lck	0.57	0.19	23.75	3.02	15.35	
Yes	0.68	0.08	4815.83	170.67	351.58	
Lyn/Hck selectivity	16.7	>9.3	2	6.9	23.8	
Phagocytosis HMC3	EC ₅₀ (μ M)	0.82	0.54	0.46	1.14	0.09
	Max (%)	472	304	182	192	98**
Phagocytosis BV2	EC ₅₀ (μ M)	Inactive	Inactive	15.2	1.96	0.45
	Max (%)	Inactive	Inactive	ND*	238	177

^aThe IC₅₀ values were determined using the Hotspot kinase assay and converted to K_i values using the Cheng-Prusoff equation to facilitate direct comparison (n=1 except for Lyn and Hck).^bcould not fit inhibition data. *maximum phagocytosis % could not determined due to cytotoxicity at higher concentrations. **baseline started at 70% . (n=2 for TAD-000640 and TAD-0410368 phagocytosis)

Saracatinib has been employed in various clinical trials as a potential therapeutic for Alzheimer's disease, with its inhibitory activity on Fyn serving as the fundamental rationale.^{49,50} However, our findings suggest that it is a broad-spectrum SFK inhibitor in-vitro, and thus, the phenotypic outcome of any implications cannot be attributed to Fyn inhibition alone. Saracatinib is also one of the two type I inhibitors that demonstrated significant phagocytosis induction capability in HMC3 cells, yet showed no activity in BV2 cells. This discrepancy could stem from differences in the kinases targeted by Saracatinib within these two cell lines. Therefore, to gain further insight into the cellular kinase targets of Saracatinib in HMC3 and BV2 cells, as well as to understand the HMC3-specific phagocytosis induction, we proceeded with a kinome profiling experiment.

Kinome Profiling of Saracatinib in HMC3 and BV2 Cells

Kinome profiling is a powerful tool for understanding kinase activity in complex biological systems⁵¹. This high-throughput technique allows for the simultaneous interrogation of the activities of numerous kinases within a cellular context, providing a global view of the functional kinase network in a given biological sample.⁵²⁻⁵³ In the context of the current study, kinome profiling can offer insights into the target spectrum of Saracatinib in HMC3 and BV2 cells, and potentially reveal why Saracatinib-induced phagocytosis is specific to HMC3 cells. To that end, we obtained the kinome profiles of Saracatinib at three different concentrations (1 μ M, 100 nM, and 10 nM) in HMC3 and BV2 cell lysates, and the results are

shown in **Figure 6**. The detailed procedure for kinome profiling used in this study can be found elsewhere.^{52, 54 53, 55} Briefly, BV2 and HMC3 cells were lysed using Lysis buffer (50 mM HEPES, 150 mM NaCl, 0.5% Triton X-100, 1 mM EDTA, 1 mM EGTA, pH 7.5, supplemented with CComplete protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche) and 1% phosphatase inhibitor cocktails 2 and 3 (Sigma), 10 mM NaF, 2.5 mM NaVO₄), and after clarification by sonication and centrifugation, the protein concentration was adjusted to 2 mg in 1.8mL. Saracatinib was introduced into lysate at a final volume of 2 mL and final concentrations of 10 nM, 100 nM, and 1 μ M (including a DMSO control), in biological triplicate, followed by incubation for 30 min at 4°C on a rocking platform. Subsequently, the mixture was raised to 1M NaCl by the addition of 5M NaCl and gravity-flowed over affinity chromatography columns containing equilibrated multiplexed kinase inhibitor beads (MIBs). Columns were washed sequentially with 5 mL high-salt (1M NaCl) lysis buffer, 5 mL lysis buffer (150 mM NaCl), 5 mL lysis buffer with 0.1% SDS, before two rounds of elution of bound fraction with 0.5 mL of 0.5% SDS, 1% beta-mercaptoethanol, 100 mM Tris-HCl, pH 6.8 for 15 min at 95°C. Eluate was treated with 5 mM DTT for 25 min at 60°C and 20 mM iodoacetamide for 30 min in the dark at room temperature. After spin concentration of the ~1 mL sample using Amicon Ultra-4 (10k cut-off) to ~ 100-150 μ L, proteins were extracted by methanol chloroform, dried in a SpeedVac, and resuspended in 50 mM HEPES, pH 8.0. Tryptic digests were performed overnight, extracted 4x with 1 mL water-saturated ethyl acetate to remove detergent, dried, and de-salted using C-18 spin columns (Agilent) and spun through an empty 10 μ M frit BioPureSPN column (Nest Group). Peptides were resuspended in 0.1% formic acid and approximately 40% of the final peptide suspension injected onto a Thermo Easy Spray 75 μ M x 25 cm C-18 column (ES902) and separated on a 131 min gradient (5-40% acetonitrile) using an EASY-nLC 1200 instrument. The Thermo Scientific Orbitrap Exploris 480 ESI parameters were as follows: Full Scan – Resolution 120,000, Scan range 375-1500 m/z, RF Lens 40%, AGC Target - Custom (Normalized AGC Target, 300%), 60 sec maximum injection time, Filters – Monoisotopic peak determination: Peptide, Intensity Threshold 5.0e3, Charge State 2-5, Dynamic Exclusion 30 sec, Data Dependent Mode – 20 Dependent scans, ddMS2 – Isolation Window 2 m/z, HCD Collision Energy 30%, Resolution 30,000, AGC Target – Custom (100%), maximum injection time 60 sec. Raw files were processed for label-free quantification (LFQ) by MaxQuant (version 1.6.11.0) MaxLFQ using a UniProt/Swiss-Prot human (HMC3) or mouse (BV2) database with fixed carbidomethyl (C) and variable oxidation (M) and acetyl (protein N-terminal) modifications, match time window 3 min. LFQ intensities for all kinome.org annotated kinases with at least two razor+unique peptides were imported into Perseus software (version 1.6.10.50), log₂ transformed, filtered to include annotated kinases and missing values imputed from the normal distribution for each column using default parameters (width 0.3, down shift 1.8) if three valid values were present in at least one treatment group. The log₂ LFQ intensities were used for two-sample t-tests in R and log₂ fold change and -log₁₀ P values used for volcano plots.

Figure 6. Multiplexed inhibitor bead (MIB) kinome profiling of Saracatinib at 100 nM in **(A)** HMC3 and **(B)** BV2 cells.

According to the results, saracatinib targets a group of SFKs, TGF β -receptor family kinases, and RIP kinases in both HMC3 and BV2 cells. Specifically, among the SFKs, it primarily targets Fyn, Lyn, and Src kinases in both cell types while specifically targeting Yes and Hck kinases in HMC3 and BV2 cells, respectively. The three targeted TGF β -receptor family serine/threonine kinases are ACVR1, TGFBR1, and BMPR1A. In addition, saracatinib also targets receptor-interacting serine/threonine kinases, specifically RIPK2 in both cell lines and RIPK3 in the BV2 cell line only. Given that Hck is observed as a target of saracatinib solely in HMC3 cells and considering its importance in phagocytosis, we examined the list of kinases reported in our kinome profiling experiment. Interestingly, Hck was absent from the list of kinases identified for HMC3 cells, indicating little to no expression of Hck in these cells. This suggests that the phagocytosis activity of HMC3 cells depends less on Hck activity compared to BV2 cells and explains the HMC3-specific phagocytosis induction of saracatinib.

Conclusions:

In this study, we evaluated a selection of kinase inhibitors from the literature against Lyn and Hck using the hotspot kinase assay. Our primary aim was to validate their reported activities in a common assay and assess the Lyn and Hck selectivities. Type I kinase inhibitors, such as Saracatinib and Bosutinib, exhibited potent Lyn inhibitory activities in the pM range, while type II inhibitors, such as Masitinib and Imatinib, displayed selectivities favoring Lyn over Hck by more than 20-fold. Both Saracatinib and Bosutinib significantly induced phagocytosis in HMC3 cells, whereas Type II inhibitors, including Masitinib, Bafetinib, and Nilotinib, showed moderate activity in both HMC3 and BV2 cells. Although these compounds exhibited Lyn/Hck selectivities, screening against an array of SFKs revealed their broad-spectrum SFK inhibitor activities. Kinome profiling of Saracatinib confirmed its targeting of Lyn in both HMC3 and BV2 cells. Moreover, the absence of Hck expression in HMC3 cells underscored the cell type and context-dependent nature of phagocytosis activity. The compounds and data in this study will serve researchers aiming to develop more potent and Lyn-selective inhibitors.

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